

AWARENESS, MOTIVATION, AND TAX COMPLIANCE OF SELF-EMPLOYED INDIVIDUALS AND PROFESSIONALS

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Awareness, Motivation, and Tax Compliance of Self-Employed Individuals and Professionals

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Abstract

This study determined the level of awareness, degree of motivation, and tax compliance of self-employed individuals and professionals in General Santos City, and whether the level of awareness and degree of motivation have a significant relationship with tax compliance. This research used a descriptive and correlational design, utilizing the survey as the primary data-gathering method. Data from the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) were also used to support the findings. Multiple regression was used to analyze the data. The majority of the respondents are sole proprietors engaged in services and earn an annual income of Php 250,000 and below. The level of tax awareness was determined to be high. The respondents were intrinsically motivated to comply with tax regulations at a high level and extrinsically motivated at a very high level. The level of compliance was determined to be high. This was attributed to the programs of the BIR such as briefings, social media updates, tax quizzes, surveillance operations, tax mapping, dialogues, and caravans. The regression analysis reveals that only the level of awareness and the degree of extrinsic motivation have a significant relationship with the level of tax compliance and that the level of awareness has a bigger strength in terms of affecting tax compliance. Based on these results, a tax awareness program was designed to increase tax compliance. The program focuses on tax education campaigns and the integration of income taxation in senior high and non-business college curricula. Further studies on other factors affecting tax compliance were proposed.

Keywords: *income taxation, tax awareness, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, tax compliance*

Introduction

Compliance with tax laws and regulations have always been a challenge both for tax authorities and taxpayers. According to Dom, Custers, Davenport, & Prichard (2022), many nations' tax collections continue to fall short of what is required to fund the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. Tax collection is usually marked by a great deal of unfairness and inequality, with particularly poor compliance and enforcement among the wealthy and considerable, but ignored, lower-income groups (Dom, Custers, Davenport, & Prichard, 2022). Decreased public revenues due to tax evasion and noncompliance with tax laws limit the capacity of governments to implement policies and provide public services. In China, one of the main reasons for tax evasion and noncompliance behavior is the widespread disregard for tax law by taxpayers. Similarly, just approximately 2% of Indians pay income taxes, which generates inflation by increasing India's budget deficit. India has poor tax compliance due to a number of interrelated problems, including complex and unclear tax laws, ineffective tax administration, and an overreliance on enforcement instruments. In Brazil, tax evasions are influenced by flaws in the tax system, ineffective tax administration and enforcement, a lack of appropriate rules, and abuse of tax havens (Mo, 2003).

In the Philippines, despite launching digital changes to broaden tax payment alternatives, the Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) fell short of the P2.08 trillion goal set by the Cabinet-level Development Budget Coordination Committee. According to the Department of Finance's fiscal plan, the government should increase tax collection to P3.3 trillion in 2022 to reduce the budget deficit to 7.7% of GDP (Rosales, 2022). As of the end of January 2022, the Philippine national government's total outstanding debt was P12.03 trillion.

Due to net availment of both domestic and external debt, the national government's overall debt climbed by P301.12 billion in January 2022, or 2.6 percent. External borrowing accounted for 30.4 percent of total debt, while domestic borrowing accounted for 69.6 percent (Bureau of the Treasury, 2022). As a result of the COVID-19 outbreak, the Philippine government's borrowing reached more than P12 trillion for the first time (Manuel, 2022). In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, which slashed earnings, the Philippines borrowed even more, obtaining a total of \$2 billion in low-interest loans from multilateral lenders in 2021 to purchase vaccinations and booster shots to vaccinate the majority of the people for free.

The Department of Finance (DOF) plans to release a fiscal consolidation package to repay and reduce the country's debt while also decreasing the budget deficit, which is at an all-time high, as a result of higher spending but fewer tax and non-tax receipts due to the prolonged pandemic. With high debt, a large budget deficit, and still recovering revenues, the fiscal consolidation plan may include new or higher taxes, expenditure cuts in non-priority areas, and other measures (De Vera, 2022).

Despite the country's massive debt, the Department of Finance opposes tax increases. Instead, the focus should be on improving tax administration and collection (Morales & Davies, 2022). Of the yearly BIR collections, individual income taxes account for around 21% on average. Self-employed individuals and professionals (SEPs) are typically regarded as "hard-to-tax" individuals and have been scrutinized by the BIR in recent years. The withholding mechanism is responsible for more than 90% of individual income taxes. Employers deduct taxes owing from compensation income earners from employee salaries on a regular basis. Withholding on wages is a way of collecting income tax from compensation income earners at the point of receipt. Employers are designated as withholding

agents. Only about 6% of overall individual income tax collections come from voluntary assessment or self-declaration of income and expenses subject to tax-related data presentation such as books of accounts and official receipts. This voluntary disclosure of income provides SEPs with the opportunity to reduce their tax liabilities by under-declaring income. Despite the BIR's best efforts to fully capture the "hard-to-tax" group, many SEPs manage to evade paying the correct amount of tax. Because SEPs voluntarily declare their own income and file their own tax returns, they have the chance to avoid and/or evade taxes (Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department, 2016).

Despite the BIR's best efforts to fully capture the "hard-to-tax" group, it remains unclear how to make SEPs conform with tax laws. It is commonly known that initiatives to promote tax compliance necessitate enforcement improvements such as credible punishments for individuals and businesses who fail to pay their full legal obligations (The World Bank, 2022). On the other hand, high tax morale, the innate drive to pay taxes based on people's sense of duty to their state, is highly connected with high rates of compliance with tax responsibilities (Rostain & Regan, 2014). Similarly, taxpayers' comprehension and willingness to comply with the law and pay the appropriate taxes encourage voluntary tax compliance (Cu, 2017). In order to determine whether awareness actually promotes tax compliance and whether external or internal motivation foster conformity with tax regulations, this study examined the awareness, motivation, and tax compliance of SEPs in General Santos City. The study's findings will lead to recommendations that will assist the government in increasing tax revenue and reducing the budget deficit.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of awareness, degree of motivation, and tax compliance of self-employed individuals and professionals. Specifically, this research answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of self-employed individuals and professionals in terms of:
 - 1.1. type of business; and
 - 1.2. annual income?
2. What is the level of tax awareness of self-employed individuals and professionals?
3. What is the degree of motivation of self-employed individuals and professionals to comply with tax regulations in terms of
 - 2.1. intrinsic motivation; and
 - 2.2. extrinsic motivation?
4. What is the level of tax compliance of self-employed individuals and professionals?
5. Do the level of awareness and degree of motivation significantly influence the level of tax compliance?
6. What programs are implemented by the Bureau of Internal Revenue to increase tax compliance?
7. Given the findings of the study, what program can be recommended?

Methodology

This research utilized a descriptive and correlational design to analyze the relationships among the variables level of awareness, degree of motivation, and level of tax compliance, specifically among self-employed individuals and professionals in General Santos City. The use of this research design was grounded in the nature of the research objectives, which sought to describe the existing patterns of relationships among these variables rather than establish causal links. The correlational research design is particularly suitable for understanding the relationships between levels of awareness, motivation, and compliance with tax laws, as the study aimed to examine these relationships in a real-world context rather than in a controlled experimental environment. Given the local context, where tax compliance may vary based on individual knowledge of tax laws and personal motivation, this research design allowed for the identification of trends or patterns that might be applicable to this specific group of self-employed individuals and professionals. The descriptive approach through surveys helped to collect data on these variables, while multivariate statistical techniques were employed to analyze the relationships among them. While the study cannot definitively establish causality, the findings contribute valuable insights into the relationships between these key factors in the context of General Santos City, leading to conclusions and recommendations for improving tax compliance strategies in similar settings.

The respondents were self-employed individuals and professionals (SEPs) from General Santos City. These SEPs came from the various business sectors and professions. Using simple random sampling in selecting the respondents, the researchers distributed and subsequently retrieved hard copies of the questionnaire to the different barangays of General Santos City. Google questionnaire was also sent online to randomly selected SEPs. Simple random sampling is the most basic sampling technique, in which each individual is chosen at random and every member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample (Easton & McColl, 1997). This method eliminates selection bias and produces representative samples (Gravetter & Forzano, 2016). The researchers used Cochran's Formula (Cochran, 1977) to determine the sample size since the population of SEPs in General Santos City is unknown. Using Cochran's formula, the sample size at 95% level of confidence was 385, however only 359 responded positively to the survey. Nonetheless, this figure provided a sufficient number of observations for the study's results to be considered reliable.

The researchers used a self-structured questionnaire in printed and Google forms as the instrument for collecting the necessary data for this study. The questionnaire contained guided responses containing descriptive data on various aspects which helped in determining the profile of SEPs in General Santos City, their level of awareness, degree of motivation, and level of tax compliance. The

questionnaire contained carefully planned written questions related to the topic, which when submitted to and answered accurately by the respondents, supplied sufficient data to complete this research.

The questionnaire was validated by experts in order to enhance it. The survey instrument was validated by two categories of specialists: topic experts with in-depth knowledge and competence in taxation, and survey methodologists with expertise in collecting the most reliable data for the research questions. These expert opinions influenced the content and format of the questionnaire. Results of the validity test revealed a mean of 4.21, interpreted as “excellent”. This means that the questionnaire's content and structure were rated as excellent in terms of clarity of direction and items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of items per category, attainment of the purpose, objectivity, and scale and evaluation rating system.

Pre-test was administered to a pilot test of 35 samples, which were excluded from the actual respondents, to measure internal consistency or reliability using Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability, or internal consistency of a set of scale or test items. The consistency with which a measurement gauges a concept is referred to as its reliability, and Cronbach's alpha measures the strength of that consistency (Goforth, 2016). The pre-test showed a Cronbach's alpha of .72 which indicates an acceptable level of reliability or internal consistency. The scales were also tested post hoc, and showed a Cronbach's alpha of .804.

After obtaining an acceptable internal consistency from the pilot test, approval was obtained from the Research Council to conduct the actual testing. The survey questionnaires were then distributed online and in hard copies to randomly selected SEPs in General Santos City. The respondents answered the questionnaires after providing their informed consent of participating voluntarily in the research. After collecting the answered questionnaires, data obtained were recorded for analysis and interpretation.

Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages were used to summarize the profile of the SEPs. This measure determined the distribution of the respondents as to their profile. The mean was used to measure the level of awareness, degree of motivations, and level of tax compliance.

SPSS version 20 was used to handle the data. To further analyze the gathered data, multiple regression was used. Multiple linear regression modeled the relationship among awareness, motivation, and tax compliance by fitting a linear equation to observed data. Every value of the independent variable x , awareness, and x_2 , motivation, was associated with a value of the dependent variable y , tax compliance. Tests on collinearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and sufficiency were made to satisfy the assumptions of regression analysis in order to make the outcome of the analysis valid.

The researchers took all necessary steps to ensure that ethical considerations were prioritized throughout the study. Participants were fully informed of the research's purpose and were given the freedom to participate voluntarily, without any pressure or coercion. Strict measures were taken to protect their confidentiality and privacy. Sensitive information was handled with the highest level of care, ensuring data security and anonymity. Additionally, the research was conducted with integrity, free of plagiarism, and the results were presented accurately and transparently.

Results and Discussion

Profile of Self-Employed Individuals and Professionals

Of the 359 self-employed individuals and professionals who responded to the survey, 17% are rendering services as professionals, 52% are sole proprietors engaged in service businesses, 11% are rendering mix services both as professionals and as sole proprietors, 14% are in merchandising businesses, and 6% are into manufacturing.

Almost half of the respondents, at 48%, earn an annual income of Php 250,000 and below, while 8% earn over Php 8,000,001 a year. 12% of the respondents earn between Php 250,001 to Php 400,000, 10% between Php 400,001 to Php 800,000, 10% between Php 800,001 to P2,000,000, and 12% between Php 2,000,001 to Php 8,000,000.

Majority of the self-employed individuals and professionals who responded to the survey, are sole proprietors engaged in service businesses. Because it can be established by only one person, people who choose a sole proprietorship value the ease of administration and flexibility that come with this kind of business structure (White & Main, 2022). In the Philippines, 91.2% of Filipino households engaged in entrepreneurial activities in 2018 were sole proprietorships (Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas, 2018). Correspondingly, almost half of the respondents of this study earn an annual income of Php 250,000 and below. This aligns with the findings of the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (2018), where the average annual income of households in the Philippines is roughly Php 130,000.

Level of Tax Awareness of Self-Employed Individuals and Professionals

The level of tax awareness was rated by the respondents at a factor average of 3.56, described as highly aware, with a standard deviation of 0.90. The indicator “In general, the income of self-employed individuals and professionals is subject to the graduated income tax rates” was rated the highest with a mean of 4.03, while the indicator “To claim the OSD, it must be selected in the first quarter income tax return and cannot be revoked during the taxable year” was rated the lowest at 3.26.

Results on the level of tax awareness show that the respondents understand the tax regulations at a high level. This supports the findings

of Paco and Quezon (2022), who obtained evidence that micro and small enterprises were very aware of BIR requirements. However, results suggest that the respondents have only a moderate level of awareness on the optional standard deduction (OSD). Despite the advantages of using OSD, few taxpayers use the approach (Pilotin, 2019). A taxpayer's profit margin must be more than 60% in order to qualify for tax benefits under OSD. As a result, taxpayers who have significantly smaller profit margins, often those in trading or manufacturing businesses, will not claim OSD (Pilotin, 2019).

Degree of Motivation

The degree of motivation of self-employed individuals and professionals to comply with tax regulations was evaluated in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. These were measured using a semantic differential scale with five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest.

The degree of intrinsic motivation was rated by the respondents at a factor average of 4.17, described as highly motivated, with a standard deviation of 0.76. The respondents are very highly motivated by the indicator "It is my duty as a Filipino", which was rated at 4.36, while the indicator "I derive a sense of happiness from it" provided the lowest motivation at 3.92.

Evidence from the study indicated that the respondents are intrinsically motivated at a high level. The findings agree with that of Pacaldo and Ferrer (2020), where entities outside the capital city of Manila exhibited higher tax morale compared to firms in Metro Manila. Further, the respondents are very highly motivated to pay taxes because of their duty as a Filipino. This supports the findings of Bani-Khalid, Alshira'h, and Malek (2022) who suggested that tax compliance is improved with high levels of patriotic feelings for one's country. Deriving a sense of happiness from complying with tax regulations provided the lowest motivation. This contradicts with the study of Akay, et al. (2012) where individuals were found to have higher subjective well-being when paying taxes. In the Philippines, taxes are viewed as burdens and regarded as constraints to entrepreneurial undertaking (Velasco, et al., 2017).

The degree of extrinsic motivation was rated by the respondents at a factor average of 4.39, described as very highly motivated, with a standard deviation of 0.70. The respondents are motivated the most by the indicator "I do not want my license to be revoked or my business shut down", which was rated at 4.53, while the indicator "I do not want to feel guilty" provided the lowest motivation at 4.20.

The results also reveal that the respondents are extrinsically motivated at a very high level. The respondents are very highly motivated by the fear of having their license revoked or their business shut down. According to the findings of Paco and Quezon (2022), penalties are the highest factor that affects taxpayer compliance. The BIR can suspend and close operations for businesses that violate the tax code (Buted, 2018). Income earners risk criminal prosecution if they decline to provide official receipts and invoices. They can also be jailed if they willfully fail to pay taxes (Buted, 2018).

Level of Tax Compliance

The level of tax compliance of self-employed individuals was measured using a semantic differential scale with five as the highest and one as the lowest. The level of tax compliance was rated by the respondents at a factor average of 3.92, described as highly complied, with a standard deviation of 0.93. The respondents are very highly compliant with the indicator "I have registered my self-employment with the BIR by accomplishing BIR form 1901 along with the required attachments", which was rated at 4.35, while the indicator "I keep the required book of accounts for at least 10 years" was complied with the least but still on a high level at 3.64.

Evidence from the study shows that the respondents are complying with tax requirements at a high level. The respondents are very highly compliant with the registration of their self-employment with the BIR by accomplishing BIR form 1901 along with the required attachments, while keeping the required book of accounts for at least 10 years was complied with the least but still on a high level. These findings are consistent with the study of Paco and Quezon (2022) which revealed that micro and small enterprises comply with BIR requirements to a large extent.

Influence of Level of Awareness and Degree of Motivation to Level of Tax Compliance

For each one-level increase in the level of awareness, the mean level of tax compliance is estimated to increase by .492. For each one-degree increase in the degree of extrinsic motivation, the mean level of tax compliance is expected to increase by .388. If the level of tax awareness and the degree of extrinsic motivation are zero, the mean level of tax compliance is equal to .467. Of the two independent variables, level of awareness has the bigger standardized coefficient Beta of .477.

After testing the explanatory and predictive power of the independent variables level of awareness and degree of motivation to the dependent variable level of tax compliance, the multiple regression analysis show that the degree of intrinsic motivation was excluded from the model. Hence, there is no significant relationship between the level of tax compliance and the degree of intrinsic motivation. This is contrary to the findings of Ghani, Hamid, Sanusi, & Shamsuddin (2020) and Timothy and Abbas (2021) where the taxpayers' level of tax compliance is positively associated with their level of tax morality. This finding also diverges from that of Onu, Oats, and Kirchler (2018), Gangl, et al. (2015), and Dwenger, Kleven, Rasul, and Rincke (2016), where intrinsic motivation but not extrinsic motivation positively predicts self-reported tax compliance.

Results of the multiple regression analysis also disclose that of the two independent variables level of awareness and degree of extrinsic motivation, the level of awareness has the bigger strength in terms of affecting the level of tax compliance. Further, there is only a

moderate positive linear relationship between the variables because only 41.6% of the variation in the level of tax compliance is explained by the independent variables level of awareness and degree of extrinsic motivation. This means that 58.4% of the variability in level of tax compliance is due to other factors other than what is accounted for by the linear regression model.

As results of the study showed that tax awareness affects tax compliance, improvements in the availability of information from the Bureau of Internal Revenue and increased public opportunities to demand accountability are as a consequence, necessary to promote tax compliance (Fjeldstad & Heggstad, 2012). As findings also indicate that extrinsic motivation drives tax compliance, policies to impose stiffer penalties for non-compliance or grant awards for compliant behavior are imperative. Evidence from the study also suggests that there are other factors affecting tax compliance over and above tax awareness and extrinsic motivation. This implies the need to further study these factors. Factors such as perception of justice and trust in public authorities (Timothy & Abbas, 2021; Farrar & Hausserman, 2016; Petros, Drogalas, Karagiorgos, & Chlorou, 2019; Gangl, et al., 2015; Jae-Young & Moon, 2022) could also affect tax compliance. In the Philippines, the high cost of compliance (Sales, 2017) for instance contributes to the difficulty in paying taxes. Further, complex tax regulations must be followed by professionals and small to medium-sized organizations. Tax collection in the Philippines is complicated, following the adoption of several rules and numerous compliance procedures (Cu, 2017). Policies to simplify procedures and fee structures and harmonization of central and local government taxation could be all necessary to promote tax compliance (Fjeldstad & Heggstad, 2012).

Programs Implemented by the Bureau of Internal Revenue

According to Cubelo (2023), the BIR Revenue District Office (RDO) 110 conducts face-to-face briefings on newly registered taxpayers every Wednesday at the BIR General Santos City building. To reach more audience through social media, a series of updates on new regulations and deadlines are also posted on the official Facebook page of RDO 110. Tax quizzes are also performed on walk-in clients visiting their offices. Because the district has reached its goal for the taxable year 2022 with an excess of 2.39% and a 17.59% increase compared to the previous year, Cubelo (2023) believes their series of campaigns and making the bureau more visible motivated taxpayers to declare and remit the correct taxes on time.

The BIR RDO 110 is also closely monitoring and calling for the compliance of registered taxpayers whose remittances have drastically decreased. It is also conducting surveillance operations, tax mapping drives, tax dialogues, and tax caravans. Surveillance operations may be covert, overt, or short-duration. Covert surveillance is a clandestine and undercover observation of the business operations of a taxpayer for a particular period and is performed before inventory taking of documents, while in overt surveillance, inventory-taking is completed before monitoring the business activities. A short-duration surveillance is a tax compliance check where a taxpayer is observed for compliance with registration requirements (Orculo, 2022). Tax mapping, or Tax Compliance Verification Drive, is an enforcement program of the BIR to determine the registration compliance of business entities. Here the BIR revenue officers verify compliance with basic administrative regulations such as certificate of registration, annual registration fee, ask for receipt signage, authority to print receipts, registration of cash register and point of sale machines and computerized accounting system, registration of books of accounts, compliance with bookkeeping regulations, and display of registration notices (P & A Grant Thornton, 2022). In tax dialogues, BIR personnel meet with representatives of associations or groups to discuss and answer questions regarding tax regulations (Department of Finance, 2017). The BIR also organizes tax caravans where motorcade campaigns are conducted across municipalities to encourage taxpayers to pay taxes promptly and correctly (Galang, 2023). These strategies according to Cubelo (2023) were effective in attaining their collection goals. Aside from making taxpayers aware of their responsibilities, they also impart the consequences of not paying the correct taxes. However, Cubelo (2023) admits that the compliance of self-employed individuals and professionals is far from perfect. Aside from not having personal professionals to monitor their compliance, they are not educated enough on their tax responsibilities. Thus the BIR RDO 110 is eager to do more campaigns and seminars to educate them. Although the bureau is far from what it desires, it is making its way to get there (Cubelo, 2023).

Conclusions

The study was conducted to find out how knowledgeable, motivated, and tax-compliant self-employed individuals and professionals in General Santos City are about their tax obligations and whether awareness, external enforcement or internal willingness encourage conformity with tax laws. The study was able to gather data from 359 self-employed individuals and professionals. The research proposed that the level of awareness and degree of motivation do not significantly influence the level of tax compliance. After the multiple regression analysis, only the level of awareness and the degree of extrinsic motivation are considered to have a significant relationship to the level of tax compliance. Furthermore, there is only a moderate positive linear relationship between the variables and more than half of the variability in the level of tax compliance can be explained by factors other than the level of awareness and degree of extrinsic motivation. A tax awareness campaign program was proposed to increase tax compliance.

The proposed program should be adopted by the Bureau of Internal Revenue. Increasing the awareness of self-employed individuals and professionals will improve tax compliance. Tax compliance can be enhanced by tax administrators by adopting more straightforward communication (Tsankova, Luts, Spinnewijn, De Neve, & Imbert, 2021). Using simplified language to explain the tax procedures will enable better awareness and understanding of tax laws. Moreover, as the study suggests, there is a need to introduce taxation in non-accounting fields that produce future professionals. Integrating income taxation in senior high and non-business college curricula will equip future income earners with a fundamental awareness of taxation laws. Furthermore, since an increase in the degree

of extrinsic motivation also increases the level of tax compliance, the bureau can strengthen the imposition of penalties to enforce tax compliance. The threat of having licenses revoked or businesses closed can deter non-compliance attitudes (Mohdali, Isa, & Yusoff, 2014).

The data provided by the Bureau of Internal Revenue showed that close monitoring is done on registered taxpayers and walk-in clients. However, no proactive efforts are made on unregistered income earners. Many home-based businesses are not visible even if the bureau conducts tax mapping drives. But these businesses are detectable online. As Dominguez (2022), pointed out, the informal sector and the digital economy must all be included in the tax net. The bureau should invest resources in the monitoring of home-based and online businesses to enforce tax compliance.

Since the study found that more than half of the variability in the level of tax compliance can be explained by factors other than the level of awareness and degree of extrinsic motivation, future research should focus on exploring these factors. Tax administrators should not only focus on tax awareness campaigns and increasing penalties to enforce compliance. More studies should be conducted to find the variables that affect tax compliance. Moreover, the study can be replicated in other areas of the country or on a nationwide scale. Qualitative studies on the experiences of taxpayers are also recommended to further improve the field of taxation.

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